

1. Title, nature and duration of research

Title of research: *Transnational knowledge networks in higher education policymaking*

- Case study
 Follow-up study

Duration of research: 1 September 2021 – 31 August 2025

Duration of data processing: 1 September 2021 – 31 December 2040

2. Data controller

- Research will be conducted under an employment contract with Tampere University, indicating the University as the data controller.

Tampere University Foundation sr
33014 Tampere University
Kalevantie 4, 33100 Tampere
Business ID: 2844561-8

3. Contact person regarding the research registry

Name Jaakko Kauko
Address Åkerlundinkatu 5, 33014, Tampere University
Phone number +358 50 318 7788
Email address jaakko.kauko@tuni.fi

4. Contact information of the Data Protection Officer

dpo@tuni.fi

5. Principal investigator or research group

The Principal Investigator is a person assigned by the Data Controller to oversee the research project's implementation. A research group may also be assigned to serve as the Principal Investigator.

Name Jaakko Kauko
Address Åkerlundinkatu 5, 33014, Tampere University
Phone number +358 50 318 7788
Email address jaakko.kauko@tuni.fi

6. Researchers

Professor Jaakko Kauko
Postdoctoral researcher Katri Eeva
Doctoral researcher Jarmo Kallunki
Researcher Paula Saarinen
University lecturer Joni Forsell
EduKnow research group, Faculty of Education, University of Tampere

7. Content of research records

Contact information:

- name
- contact information
- professional information
- their organisation

Interview data:

- Audio
- Interview transcript

Observation data:

- Notes on meeting making and in the wider context of the meeting
- Notes on possible further interviews
- Notes on the speeches
- Audio, visual, and video

8. Sources of personal data

Personal data are collected from publicly available sources. Personal data may also be obtained from the subjects themselves as part of the conduct of research. Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

9. Purpose of processing personal data

The purpose of processing personal data is scientific research.

Information from the network analysis will be combined with interview and observation data. Potential knowledge flows will be tracked by means of the network.

10. Legal basis for processing personal data

The legal basis for processing under the EU's General Data Protection Regulation, Article 6 Paragraph 1, and the Personal Data Act, section 4:

- Public interest or the exercise of official authority
 - Scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes
 - Archiving of research or cultural heritage material
- Consent

How consent can be cancelled: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

- Legal obligation of data control

Regulations: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

Legitimate interests of the Data Controller or a third party

Please specify the legitimate interests: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

Other, please specify: Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

11. Sensitive personal data (special categories of data and criminal records)

No sensitive personal data will be processed during the research project

The following types of sensitive personal data will be processed during the research project:

Racial or ethnic origin

Political opinions

Religious or political beliefs

Trade union membership

Genetic data

Biometric data to uniquely identify a person

Health data

Data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation

Will personal data concerning criminal convictions and offences be processed during the research project?

No

Yes

Legal basis for processing of sensitive personal data:

The legal basis for processing under the EU's General Data Protection Regulation, Articles 9 (special categories of personal data) and 10 (personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences), and the Personal Data Act, sections 6 and 7:

Consent of the data subject

The processing activities are related to personal data the data subject has explicitly disclosed

The processing activities are conducted for scientific or historical research in the public interest, statistical purposes, or in connection with the exercise of official authority

The processing of personal data is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest

12. Transfer or disclosure of data to external parties

Personal data will be regularly transferred or disclosed to parties other than the research group's members

The data controller must follow the university's data privacy policy and exercise special care if personal data are transferred outside the EU/EEA to countries that may not comply with the principles set out in the GDPR. Transferring personal data outside the EU/EEA must be processed in compliance with data protection requirements.

A separate agreement for processing data will be made with the transcription services.

Data from the network analysis can be processed in collaboration with an external expert. In this case, data will not be obtained permanently by anyone outside the research team.

No automated decisions will be made.

13. Data protection principles

Protection of manual materials (e.g. paper documents):

- In a locked room
- In a locked cupboard
- Other, please specify: During the collection of research data, manual data are kept to a minimum and digitised as soon as possible.

Protection of digital materials (e.g. information systems and equipment):

- usernames
- password
- multi-factor authentication (MFA)
- access management (IP address)
- collection of log data
- physical access control
- other, please specify

Processing of data that directly identify an individual:

- Directly identifiable data will be removed during the analysis stage
- The materials will be pseudonymised
- The materials will be analysed without directly removing identifiable data, because (please provide the reasons for retaining personally identifiable data): This only concerns network analysis based on publicly available information. The network is based on data that directly identify an individual.

Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

14. Processing of personal data after the research project has been concluded

- The research records will be destroyed
- The research records will be anonymised and archived without personally identifiable data
- The research records will be archived without anonymisation

Data collected from publicly available sources are stored in the Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD) without anonymisation. If separately agreed, data concerning the subject being interviewed or observed can be defined as available for a specific period (e.g. 5–20 years). Unless it is specifically agreed that interview and observation data will be archived in the FSD, they will be stored for follow-up studies in the university's secure network drive until 2040 at the latest, after which the data will be destroyed. Kirjoita tekstiä napsauttamalla tai napauttamalla tätä.

15. Data subjects' rights and possible restriction thereof

Data subjects have the following rights under the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

- Right of access
 - o Data subjects are entitled to find out which information the University holds about them or to receive confirmation that their personal data are not processed by the University.

- Right to rectification
 - o Data subjects have the right to have any incorrect, inaccurate, or incomplete personal details held by the University revised or supplemented without undue delay. In addition, data subjects are entitled to have any unnecessary personal data deleted from the University's systems.

- Right to erasure
 - o In exceptional circumstances, data subjects have the right to have their personal data erased from the Data Controller's records ('right to be forgotten').

- Right to restrict processing:
 - o In certain circumstances, data subjects have the right to request the University to restrict the processing of their personal data until the accuracy of their data, or the basis for processing their data, has been appropriately reviewed and potentially revised or supplemented.

- Right to object
 - o In certain circumstances, data subjects may at any time object to the processing of their personal data for compelling personal reasons.

- Right to data portability
 - o Data subjects have the right to obtain a copy of the personal data they have submitted to the University in a commonly used machine-readable format and transfer the data to another Data Controller.

- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority
 - o Data subjects have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority in their permanent place of residence or place of work if they consider the processing of their personal data to violate the provisions of the GDPR (EU 2016/679). In addition, data subjects may follow other administrative procedures to appeal against a decision made by a supervisory authority or seek a judicial remedy.

Contact information:

Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman

Street address: Ratapihantie 9, 6th floor, 00520 Helsinki, Finland

Postal address: PO Box 800, FI-00521 Helsinki, Finland

Switchboard: tel. +358 29 56 66700

Fax: +358 29 56 66735

Email address: tietosuoja@om.fi

The Data Controller follows a GDPR-compliant procedure to respond to subject access requests.